

AGEMERA

Critical Raw Materials for
a Resilient Europe

DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION PLAN AND VISUAL IDENTITY

Deliverable 5.1

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1. Executive Summary

1.1. AGEMERA in short

The AGEMERA project will use innovative, non-invasive methods and technologies to unlock Europe's resource potential, improve public knowledge of Critical Raw Materials, and promote sustainable mineral exploration.

The EU's transition to a low-carbon, digital economy requires innovative tools, technologies, and techniques to be used in mineral exploration. AGEMERA will conduct extensive geological and geophysical surveys, across an area of approximately 4700 km² and demonstrating 3 novel, non-invasive methods, to map resources in 6 EU countries and 1 third country (Zambia). The project will use various types of data to improve the genetic mineral system models of deposit types known to contain CRM. At the same time, an open-access SoftGIS database will be developed to gain a better understanding of people's social, cultural, environmental, and economic concerns related to mining and mineral exploration. AGEMERA will also raise awareness on the importance of CRM for the green and digital transition, by producing an educational package for schools and universities together with an online serious game and by organising public events to reach wide audiences.

1.2. Scope of the Communication and Dissemination Plan

The AGEMERA project aims to increase knowledge on critical raw materials (CRM) deposits, potentials and capacities in Europe, and the efficacy related to mineral exploration and ore deposit characterization.

To achieve this long-term goal, the core activities of AGEMERA, together with the support of strong communication and dissemination actions, will contribute to the **transition to a climate neutral and more digitalised society and economy**.

This Communication and Dissemination plan aims to maximize the project's visibility, spread the information of its goals, activities, results while informing well-targeted audience groups of the project's outputs and their linkages to **sustainable mineral exploration**. Through effective communication, AGEMERA will increase the general public's awareness on the need for a **sustainable approach towards CRM**.

The main pillars and scope of the **communication and dissemination plan** are:

- Communicating about AGEMERA to wider audiences to increase social acceptance and awareness regarding CRM, sustainable exploration and mining practices;
- Disseminating project results among the scientific community, practitioners and policy makers;
- Reaching out to various groups of stakeholders to enhance the uptake of technologies and approaches developed in the project, and to facilitate new business model developments.

Within the project, WP5 Dissemination, Communication & Collaboration is entirely dedicated to its communication and dissemination activities. This work package includes the following tasks:

- Task 5.1: Dissemination, communication plan and visual identity
- Task 5.2: Joint dissemination actions and scientific outreach
- Task 5.3: Communication and public outreach
- Task 5.4: Collaboration and synergies

Throughout the different tasks, WP5 makes sure the project's results reach the detected target audiences thanks to an effective communication and dissemination plan, a compelling visual identity, and the support of the consortium.

2. Communication and Dissemination Plan

2.1. The Plan: An overview

AGEMERA will deploy a centralised-decentralised communication strategy. The **website** will be the focal point, where key stakeholders will be able to learn about the project and its mission, be informed about the latest activities and events, and have access to all the resources that will be developed in the project.

All communication activities will be **supported by the consortium** members in the various EU Member States and Zambia, who will be provided with the communication materials that will be produced in WP5 and invited to use them to promote the project in the national and local events they participate in. Social media will be frequently used by all Consortium members, who will share the project's news and achievements across their networks for enhanced visibility.

The **communication objectives** are:

- Promoting the project's mission through various communication activities and channels and to a wide audience
- Promoting the project's website
- Keeping consistent with the project's visual identity across all communication activities
- Exchanging knowledge and fostering collaborations with other projects and initiatives that align with our project's objectives and focus on a similar topic

2.2. Target Audience

The vast scope of the project demands for a vast target audience. From the mining industry to the secondary school teachers and students to networks and umbrella organisations, the target groups detected will be reached through tailored messages and tools.

2.2.1. Target groups

- **Private sector:** Mining and mineral exploration companies, and survey equipment suppliers potentially interested in the technological solutions, approaches and databases developed in the project.

- **Scientific field:** Researchers and scholars can utilize the knowledge developed in the project for further research on CRM and sustainable mining approaches.
- **Policy makers:** They can exploit and make use of recommendations of the project that could facilitate the development of better policies and legal frameworks regarding CRM in Europe.
- **Youth:** Secondary school students and teachers, who can benefit from the learning package developed focusing on deepening knowledge and understanding on CRM.
- **Society at large:** Raising awareness in the public is a crucial element of communications of the project, regarding increasing understanding and interest towards sustainable mining approaches and CRM.

2.2.2. Stakeholders and Networks

Table below shows the diverse audiences and the methods that will be used to reach them.

Category	Audience	Why them?	How will we reach them?
Mining companies	Early adopters	They tend to adopt novel technologies before the rest of the industry	The mining sites of the project will act as lighthouse demonstrators for the entire industry. First, early adopters will be invited to national workshops in order to hear about project results. Then, detailed technical and business cases will be disseminated to all mining companies via industry conferences and publications as part of WP5 activities
	Mainstream operators	They may take more time to adopt novel technologies	
Survey equipment suppliers	Sensor suppliers	They can distribute or license the project sensing innovations	The target sites will demonstrate the technical and commercial value of advanced sensors, technologies, and methods in mineral exploration and geological material characterization. SME-approved sensor and data analytics suppliers will be invited to follow the project progress, and regular newsletters will keep them updated about the pilots as part of WP5.
	Data analytics suppliers	They can distribute or license the project data analytics methods	
Researchers	Geophysics experts	They seek to improve their knowledge of geological models	The consortium will publish open access scientific articles and present the project results in key scientific conferences as part of WP5 activities. The academic/research partners will also generate material for educational programs related to sustainable mining.
	Mining exploration experts	They seek to develop new exploration survey methods	
Policy makers	National regulators	They are responsible for the national policy landscape	The consortium will study the regulatory landscape in the countries represented in the consortium and communicate best practices. The consortium will publish project results (SoftGIS based map of potential social, environmental, economic vulnerability) in collaboration with EU regulators. The result
	EU regulators	They are developing innovation agenda to support a more	

		competitive raw material production in Europe	of the awareness campaign will provide input for the EU Raw Material Action (ERMA) plan.
Youth	Secondary school students and teachers	They are the citizens and decision makers of the future!	The consortium will actively participate in organized exhibitions and conferences such as “Expominer”, “Geology day”, and similar activities.
Society at large	Medias	They tend to focus on high profile industry-related incidents rather than sustainability efforts	The consortium will conduct specific awareness programs towards the general public, in order to highlight the benefits of novel technologies (such as AGEMERA) on the sustainability, environmental and social friendliness of mining activities. The campaigns will include the development of specific media kits (press-release, picture libraries, videos) that can easily be reused by journalists (specialized or generalists) to reach the broader possible public.
	General Public	They perceive the mining and metal processing companies as making the least efforts to behave responsibly towards society	

2.3. Timeline

AGEMERA is a 3-year project. In order to build a community that can lead towards dissemination and eventually exploitation, the scope of the dissemination and communication activities has been set as follows:

- **Year 1: Raising awareness**
 - This will be achieved by building on the internal knowledge and contacts of the consortium and creating joint campaigns with existing networks. The purpose of this phase is to shed light on a much-debated topic.
- **Year 2: Building a community**
 - Workshops and events will help to bring AGEMERA to a more narrow and targeted audience. The aim is to start building expectations towards AGEMERA results.
- **Year 3: Conveying results**
 - Going into the third year, the project results will start to materialise and they will be widely disseminated across all channels and relevant platforms.

To maximise sustainability and impact, the partners will continue disseminating the project’s results beyond the project’s end.

2.4. Dissemination Tools and Channels

A wide variety of dissemination **tools and channels** will be used throughout AGEMERA’s lifetime to maximise the project’s impact and reach the aforementioned audiences.

The main tools and channels are the following:

- Make use of and promote the project’s distinct **visual identity** both online (websites, social media channels) and offline (printed materials)

- Spread information about the project's objectives, activities, and results through **online** (website, social media) and **offline channels** (events, workshops, seminars, etc.)
- Use the **European Commission's tools and channels** to boost the visibility of the AGEMERA messages (e.g. The European Research Executive Agency's Twitter profile: @REA_research, DG Research and Innovation Twitter profile: @EUScienceInnov, the Horizon Europe Twitter profile: @HorizonEU etc.)
- Use **national and international platforms, projects, initiatives** as intermediaries to disseminate and communicate in the Consortium's national languages
- Use **networking and collaboration** with relevant influencers, organisations, projects and initiatives
- Raise awareness about the role of Critical Raw Materials in the transition to a green, digital economy through joint **communication campaigns**, such as social media campaigns, joint events/workshops

2.4.1. Visual Identity

AGEMERA has a distinct visual identity that was created by WP5 leader, GEONARDO, at the beginning of the project. GEONARDO will guide the Consortium members in properly making use of the visual identity to ensure a **harmonious image** in all communication activities. A unified visual identity is essential to support the unique voice and tone of the AGEMERA.

Apart from the Brand Guidelines, the GEONARDO team has created several templates (Word, Excel, PowerPoint) that align with the project's visual identity and will be used by the Consortium members throughout the project's cycle.

Additionally, the Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation leaders will develop the project's website following the AGEMERA visual identity, as well as various materials (in both digital and printable formats) that can be used to introduce the audience to the project (e.g. leaflets, posters, factsheets, merchandise if needed).

2.4.2. Events

The AGEMERA consortium plans to attend numerous events throughout the project duration. While at those events, the assigned participants will communicate and disseminate the project's main outcomes and impacts with the guidance and will inform GEONARDO as the WP5 leader.

The AGEMERA partners have planned to attend the following events:

- EAGE near-surface geoscience (2022, 2023)
- EAGE annual meetings (2023, 2024)
- International Mining Geology Conference (2022, 2023)
- EGU General Assembly (2022, 2023)
- Raw Materials Summit of EIT Raw Materials (2023, 2024)
- EU Raw Materials Week (2022, 2023, 2024)
- SME annual conference and EXPO (2023, 2024)
- SOMP annual conference (2023, 2024)
- SDIMI (2024)

Partners will also participate with a stand or exhibition space in yearly business tradeshows such as Mining Tech World (2022, 2023), Euro Mine Expo (2023, 2024), and MINExpo International (2024).

2.4.3. Website

The project website will be the central element of communication about the project outputs and activities throughout the whole term. It will serve as a platform for communicating basic information to the wider public (project goals and objectives), raising awareness, and facilitating communication based on visitors' interest. The website will also display specific, up to date information about the project results, milestones, achievements, and events.

Background information about AGEMERA and its objectives, introduction to the planned activities, and the envisioned outputs will be presented in the "Who we are" sections. Basic introduction and contact information of the project partners can also be found here, together with the introduction on initiatives and projects related to AGEMERA.

The "Our work" section aims to fulfill a double objective. On one hand, it contains all the information that helps to raise awareness among the wider public. Visitors can learn about the importance and the vision behind the EU's green transition, as well as about the central role that CRM play in it. On the other hand, the section introduces the project's approach towards mineral exploration. It invites the visitors to boost their knowledge on CRM potential through introducing the project sites and planned activities, from the geological and socio-economic point of view.

We aim to share all the publications and Deliverables in the "Tools and resources" section to ensure high visibility of the project outputs.

Sections like "Media" and "Blogs & Events" are dedicated to informing the public about all the news, events, and activities, either recent or upcoming, related to the project. These sections have high importance in our communication, because here visitors can gain up to date information on all future activities and see what has happened so far in the project. The social media channels are also integrated here, which makes it easier for visitors to access. Also, in the "Contact us" section we provide various ways for the visitors to get in contact with us, including our newsletter option.

Image 1 AGEMERA website homepage design

AGEMERA's website will include the following sections:

- **Who we are** section, presenting the project's mission and its goals, the background of the project, the methodology and what differentiates AGEMERA from other projects, its partners and related projects or initiatives with whom the project can collaborate

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- **Our work** section, detailing the project’s focus on both identifying new mineral deposits with the help of new technologies, and on raising awareness of critical raw materials
- **Tools and resources** section, listing all the materials developed in the project, from deliverables and scientific papers to the online serious game and the courses on critical raw materials that will be disseminated in schools and universities
- **News, blogs, and events** section, dedicated to the latest updates from the projects, events that AGEMERA was present in, blog articles about different topics relevant to the project, or guest posts from collaborators
- **Contact page**, where users can find the contact details where they can get in touch with the project coordinators, as well as the links to our social media channels (which will also be included in the website’s footer section)

2.4.4. Partners’ Websites

The consortium partners’ websites will also be used to promote the projects. Partners are encouraged to refer to the project on their own websites, too.

Partner name	Website
University of Oulu, Finland	https://www.oulu.fi/en
University of Lapland, Finland	https://www.ulapland.fi/en
University of Zagreb, Croatia	http://www.unizg.hr/homepage/
University of Zambia, IWRM Centre	https://www.unza.zm/schools/mines/departments/integrated-water
Tallinn University of Technology	https://taltech.ee/en
Geological Institute at Bulgarian Academy of Sciences	https://www.geology.bas.bg/en
CSIC – Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas	https://www.csic.es/en
Technische Universität Bergakademie Freiberg	https://tu-freiberg.de/
KGHM Cuprum Research and Development Centre	https://kghmcuprum.com/en/
Lithica	https://lithica.net/
Radai	https://radai.fi/
Muon Solutions	http://muon-solutions.com/
Opt/Net	https://opt-net.eu/
Geonardo Environmental Solutions	https://geonardo.com/
Latitude 66 Cobalt	https://lat66.com/en/
Bauxite Mines Jajce	https://bxstone-jajce.com/en/
Bauxite Mines Posusje	TBC
MATSA	https://sandfirematsa.es/
Assarel Medet	http://www.asarel.com/en/
KGHM Polska Miedz	https://kghm.com/

2.4.5. Social Media

Social media platforms will play an important role in the communication plan of the project, because of their ability to reach wide audiences in a relatively instant way. The Twitter, LinkedIn, and Facebook pages of the project are already set up, where people can follow all relevant news and activities. Interesting news about the project and its

development, but also about the partners, will be shared, together with details of upcoming events and activities.

The four social media platforms will be updated regularly and will help:

- Promote the project’s mission and key results to non-specialist audiences
- Raise awareness of the EU Green Deal and EU policies related to mineral exploration and critical raw materials
- Identify and engage initiatives, organisations, and professionals active in the fields related to the project’s activities
- Generate new collaborations and partnerships that would contribute to the project’s mission
- Initiate discussions and increase the visibility of AGEMERA’s activities
- Promote the project brand and visual identity to newcomers
- Promote key events that will take place throughout the duration of the project
- Maintain a cohesive communication strategy across all mediums
- Spread key messages and outcomes of the project

Specific hashtags will be used to increase the visibility of the project on social media. Examples include, but are not limited to: #AGEMERA, #AGEMERAPROJECT, #HorizonEU, #EUGreenDeal, #digitaltransformation, #greentransition, #digitaleconomy, #sustainablemining, #lowcarbon.

AGEMERA LinkedIn profile

LinkedIn is best known as the social platform that allows professionals to search for jobs and network with people in their field and beyond. This translates to a more formal style of communication.

The AGEMERA LinkedIn profile will be used to introduce the project, its mission and activities to the network, share news, updates and events the project partners take part in, promote publications and resources developed in the project.

LinkedIn posts will be longer and will include media files such as pictures or videos, as data shows these boost the engagement.

- Link: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/agemeraproject/>

Image 2 AGEMERA LinkedIn profile page and post

AGEMERA Facebook profile

Compared to LinkedIn, Facebook has less of a niche aspect in terms of its purpose; it can be used by everyone to share news and updates with their followers and engage in discussions. Due to its popularity and its ability to reach a large audience, Facebook is still widely used by organisations and companies to promote their brands.

The AGEMERA Facebook profile will be used to introduce the project to the general public, raise awareness of critical raw materials and the role they play in the green transition, share news about the latest developments in the project, promote the tools developed in the project, and engage with audiences.

To help grab the viewer's attention, social media posts on Facebook will feature media files (photos, videos), emojis, and clear Call-to-Actions (see Image 3).

- Link: <https://www.facebook.com/agemeraproject/>

Image 3 AGEMERA Facebook page and post

AGEMERA Twitter profile

Twitter is perhaps best well-known for its short messages: the platform allows a number of maximum 280 characters in every tweet (while a few years ago, it even used to be 140). This restriction calls for shorter messages, in which the information is condensed in the most user-friendly way possible.

Messages are usually accompanied by emojis, pictures or videos, hashtags and links. Hashtags are a particularly powerful tool on Twitter: they are usually put in front of keywords and they help users find quickly all tweets related to a particular topic or event.

- Link: https://twitter.com/agemera_eu

Image 4 AGEMERA Twitter profile and post

AGEMERA YouTube profile

YouTube is the most popular platform for online video sharing, counting more than one billion monthly users. All types of videos can be found on the platform, from music videos to news and documentaries. The AGEMERA YouTube profile will be used to promote the videos developed in the project, interviews with project partners, short clips from events, and videos promoting the project's key results.

- Link: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCxgOsaCZTAxeFMfihw5710A>

Image 5 AGEMERA YouTube channel

2.4.6. Media coverage

The project partners are going to produce content for media during the project term, in various forms. Articles in online journals, or at local and national newspapers and agencies, are set to be carried out in specified numbers, together with interviews with various portals.

To enhance the project’s visibility among key influencers and organisations, press releases will be shared and distributed through existing platforms, networks, news portals, and mailing lists. The first press release will be shared at the beginning of the project; additional ones will be produced to announce milestones and major achievements in the project.

National and European media will be notified whenever there is a new press release to be shared. The media/press to be considered include printed newspapers and journals, television and radio, and the web. At the beginning of the project, the AGEMERA team will put together a list of media outlets to map out specific contacts that could help promote the project: journalists, editors, and bloggers. Partners will disseminate publications across their networks.

2.4.7. Intermediaries and Influencers

The AGEMERA partners will use GEONARDO – the leader of WP5 – to identify and contact key stakeholders and influencers who are active in sharing relevant news and information, are reputable in their field, and benefit from a large following. In turn, these influencers are expected to share the project’s messages with their followers.

2.4.8. Synergies and Exchange with other projects and initiatives

Developing cooperation with sister projects to enhance better dissemination and exploitation of project results are crucial for AGEMERA. In order to utilise and develop knowledge in the project effectively, it must build on previous and parallel research and results.

Moreover, the project must also seek cooperation with similar initiatives to

- Maximize effectiveness and utilization of knowledge
- Maximize visibility through joint communication and dissemination activities.

Projects identified potentially relevant to AGEMERA (EU context):

Project	Partner	Project description and cross-fertilization opportunities
CENTURION [H2020] 2021-2024	OPT	The project combines AI and Big Data Cubes to promote the monetisation of Copernicus Data. The project will provide access to the CENT-AI platform with federated connectivity to EarthServer via partner OPT in WP4.
GOLDENEYE [H2020] 2020-2023	UO OPT RAD	The project combines remote sensing and positioning technologies to take advantage of Earth observation and Earth GNSS data acquisition and processing platform for safe, sustainable and cost-efficient mining operations in Bulgaria, Finland, Germany, Kosovo and Romania. The project will provide access to the X-cubes EuroDataCube facility via partner OPT in WP4.

REEBAUX [EIT Raw Mat] 2018-2021	UZG	The project has collected data to assess the potential of the bauxite deposits and bauxite residue left behind bauxite processing industry for the production of REE in the ESEE region for European needs. The project data will be fed into WP1 and WP2 by partner UZG
RESEERVE [EIT Raw Mat] 2018-2021	UZG	The project has created West Balkan Mineral Register for primary and secondary mineral resources by mapping the mineral resources of the West Balkan countries: Croatia, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Serbia, Montenegro, North Macedonia and Albania, which are currently not included in the existing data platforms. The project data will be fed into WP1 and WP2 by partner UZG.
INFACT [H2020] 2017-2021	UO	The project has developed innovative geophysical and remote sensing technologies (magnetics, electromagnetics and infrared spectroscopy) and benchmarked those technologies in Finland, Germany and Spain. The results of these benchmarks will be fed into WP3 and WP4.
MICA [H2020] 2015-2018	N/A	EU-Raw Materials Intelligence Capacity Platform (EU-RMICP) is an excellent example to replicate to integrate information on data and methods/tools with a user interface capable of answering stakeholder questions in WP2. The project links the derived intelligence to the EU Raw Materials Knowledge Base developed in the previous FP7 Minerals4EU.
GeoERA initiative [ERA-NET]	UO	Projects EuroLithos , FRAME , MINDeSEA and Mintell4EU are supporting a more integrated and efficient management and more responsible and publicly accepted, exploitation and use of the subsurface. UO will interface with these projects to feed relevant data in WP1 and WP2.
VECTOR [Horizon Europe] 2022-2025	UO	Project VECTOR aims to develop non-invasive technological approaches for mineral exploration of CRM; also mapping social acceptance related to mining and exploration, developing an “social acceptance index”.
EIS [Horizon Europe] 2022-2025	UO	The Exploration Information Systems project foresees to develop new geomodels and novel, fast, and cost-effective spatial data analysis tools for mineral exploration analysis and modeling. It also focus on reducing footprint of exploration and mining practices, while raising awareness in the general public regarding CRM.
SECRAMET [Horizon Europe] 2022-2025	UO	SEMACRET aims to provide a clearer understanding of the EU’s mineral potential, and to develop sustainable exploration techniques for green transition (critical) raw materials hosted in orthomagmatic ore deposits. This also allows bridging the gap between academic research and the mineral exploration industry.

Initial steps of developing contacts and cooperation with multiple initiatives from the list above have already been taken. During the kick-off event in Oulu, 4-7 Oct 2022 sister project EIS, SECRAMET and VECTOR, together with GOLDENEYE were introduced and represented, facilitating networking and discussions around shared objectives and different approaches. Due to the overlapping objectives and focus, shared publications and other materials, and joint activities were concluded to be carried out. The foreseen shared activities and materials include:

- Research papers and articles
- Attendance at conferences and workshops with shared stand
- Workshops and campaign events for the public and different stakeholders
- Media presence – articles
- Social media presence - posts

2.4.9. Utilising EC Channels

The European Commission can also spread project news to its audiences, with the help of AGEMERA’s project officer. AGEMERA will also be proactive in utilising the social

media channels of the European Commission that are relevant to the project, such as The European Research Executive Agency’s Twitter profile (@REA_research), DG Research and Innovation’s Twitter profile (@EUScienceInnov), the European Research Council’s Twitter profile (@ERC_Research), to name a few. The project will also follow, like, and share news from these channels.

2.4.10. Visibility of EU funding

All visibility material will follow the EU guidelines described [here](#).

Image 6 AGEMERA Flyer

2.4.11. Scientific publications

Research articles and conference papers will be a major part of disseminating results of the project.

Partners with current and future registrations at scientific journals will publish peer-reviewed articles at i.e.: Journal of Applied Geophysics, Tectonophysics, Geophysical Journal International, Extractive Industries and Society, and the European Journal in Engineering and Education.

Partners will systematically use open access and institutional repositories to ensure the largest possible impact among researchers and policy making bodies.

2.4.12. Communication and Dissemination Materials

The AGEMERA visual identity forms the basis of the design and the development of the project's dissemination materials. GEONARDO will provide these materials to the Consortium, and in turn, these materials will be translated into the languages of the Consortium members.

GEONARDO has already created and shared most of the early-stage dissemination materials but will keep creating them throughout the projects with the support of consortium members.

Newsletter, peer-reviewed articles, workshops and games will also be part of the dissemination materials to be produced during the project.

All materials that are intended for public use will be uploaded on the website in downloadable form.

Some of the communication and dissemination materials to be produced throughout the project are:

- Set of graphics, animations, and icons to complement the communication efforts
- A package of e-templates for internal use (pptx, docx and xlsx)
- A package of e-templates for external use (pptx, docx and xlsx)
- A project "at a glance" leaflet (pdf) in digital and – where needed – printed form
- A project "at a glance" poster (pdf) in digital and – where needed – printed form
- Production of peer-reviewed articles
- Newsletter posts and disseminate results
- Educational workshops and projects; integrating project outputs into university courses + development of PhD courses + creating micro-degree programs based on the project results; development and spread of the CRM educational package
- CRM serious game

Detailed communication and dissemination activities per partner organizations:

Partner	Specific dissemination, exploitation and communication activities foreseen
UO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Present the project results and activities at EGU conferences • Organise a set of workshops w/seminars on critical raw materials as tool for the green transition • Write 3 peer-reviewed articles in journals • Communicate the project activities and updates in our social media channels
UL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Produce 2 presentations in scientific conferences of seminars

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Write 2 press releases • Reach out to mineral exploration and mining companies via Finnish Mining Association
UZG	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Write 2-4 peer-reviewed articles • Produce 4 presentations in scientific conferences - EAGE and EGU conferences • Organize workshops on the data acquisition, processing and interpretation of near-surface geophysical surveys • Organise a group of students to create and share project results via the most popular communication channels and social networks among their peers
UNZA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incorporate new methods, models and tools in the bachelor's degree programme • Write 2 peer-reviewed papers on the project, one on the methods and the other on geological models and tools of exploitation in a selected area(s) of Zambia. • Organize seminars at conferences given at the University of Zambia postgraduate and regional platforms • Involve communities and schools of the areas of operations, together with local government and industries in these areas, to create awareness programme
TT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Assemble and distribute the CRM educational package • Organise 10 seminars of 50 participants for relevant stakeholder groups (civil society, policy-makers, mining companies) • Create university micro-degree reaching 40 students-Use social media channels to increase public acceptance of mining operations in Europe • Attend external workshops, conferences, project presentations, meetings, and participate in professional networks that are related to the key topics of the proposed project • Publish a monthly newsletter about exploitation activities- • Reach 10,000 visitors for the online open-access educational package • Reach 1,000 views of educational videos, including project results
BAS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Present the project results and activities at EGU* conferences • Organise a set of w/seminars on critical raw materials as tool for the green transition • Write 3 peer-reviewed articles in journals yet to be named • Communicate the project activities and updates in our social media channels
CSIC	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-author (jointly with LITH) scientific papers related to passive seismic results • Use the knowledge from the project to create a training course for Ph.D. students
TUBAF	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Write 3-4 peer-reviewed articles in high-quality international journals • Present the research findings in 5-10 large international events and conferences in Europe and around the world (SME annual conferences in the US, Society of Mining Professors-SOMP annual conferences worldwide)- • Conduct and publish at least 3 press releases • Prepare dissemination material, both digital (banners) and printed (flyers, posters) • Disseminate the research findings via the academic and industrial network of partners around the world (contact big mining companies in Germany and countries around the world (southern Africa, Australia, east and southeast Asia, Latin America) • Use social media channels and the web page of TUBAF to disseminate the project, its activities and the research findings (create and promote success stories) • Contribute to the construction, preservation and updating of the webpage that is under development for the project. • Contribute in conducting and distributing weekly or monthly newsletters to subscribers on the official webpage of the project- • Create, preserve and monitor the cloud space for the exchange of data and information among the partners during the project, secure and easy access for consortium members, data security
CUP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Write 5 peer-reviewed open-access articles in journals with high impact factor • Use social media channels LinkedIn, Facebook and company webpage to disseminate project results. • Present the results of the project on 2 local (SEP, Poland and ZSMGiG, Poland) 4 international conferences (SGEM, EGU, WMESS, EUROCK).
LITH	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Co-author (jointly with CSIC) scientific papers related to passive seismic results • Use social media to disseminate the results of our contribution to the project

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participate in international meetings
RAD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publish papers in EAGE Near Surface geophysics Journal, EAGE Geophysical Prospecting Journal Publish in Open Research Europe – Open Access publishing Platform Present at in IAGA Electromagnetic Induction workshop Present in EAGE Near Surface Geophysics Technical Exhibition conference
MUON	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Write 4 open access peer-review papers during the project Participate to 10 conferences (including 6 talks) in different conferences, workshops, and seminars. Publish 2 articles in the Finnish geoscience magazine called “Geologi” and the Finnish mining industry magazine Materia. Publish at least 1 article in one of the Finnish science popularization magazines. disseminate our project results through radio and newspaper interviews in Finland. Use the EIT Raw Materials dissemination channels Use the Virtual Muography Institute (administered by the University of Tokyo) which includes the main developers of muography in the world Organize two seminars about muography (one for the consortium member, another for the muography community)
OPT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Publish at least 1 conference paper or presentations per year. Present at International ESA Phi-week conference in 2022 (reaching 500+ audience) Present annually the project results at the leading AI conferences in Europe (e.g. Worldwide AI Summit in Amsterdam) Present at the relevant mining and space conferences (IGRAS, ESA Phi Week, InterGEO)
GEO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Oversee the dissemination activities and contributing to local/regional (CEE) dissemination- Develop and publish the CRM serious game- Organise one local public campaign- Use company Twitter and LinkedIn accounts for communicating the project Write and disseminate 10 blog posts about the project and its activities and results-Publish annual press releases locally- - Organise seminars and workshops
LAT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support peer-reviewed open-access articles written by academic and research partners use corporate social media channels LinkedIn, Facebook and company webpage to disseminate project results. present the results of the project on local and international conferences Present the project to mining industry associations in order to foster the uptake of project results Use project materials to support joint programs with local high schools (ASSAR)
RBJ	
RBP	
MATSA	
ASSAR	
KGHM	

2.5. Key Messages

AGEMERA’s topic is highly sensible and needs to be treated with care. The generic key messages that support AGEMERA’s mission have been developed and approved with the project coordinator, OULU University.

Main key messages:

- AGEMERA will contribute to increasing Europe’s resilience through responsible, sustainable mineral exploration of Critical Raw Materials.*
- AGEMERA will help unlock Europe’s resource potential by using innovative, environmentally friendly methods and technologies, as well as extensive geophysical data, to identify new areas of mineral exploration.*
- AGEMERA will raise awareness of the crucial role Critical Raw Materials play in transforming Europe’s economy into a green, digital one.*

- *AGEMERA will monitor public opinion on mining by surveying the population in the project countries and collecting the results into an open-access database.*
- *AGEMERA will use state-of-the art methods and technologies to gain a deeper understanding of known mineral deposits and discover new ones.*
- *AGEMERA will join the mission of boosting Europe's resource autonomy*

2.6. Dissemination Principles

2.6.1. Open science

To support the spread of knowledge and the project's impact, AGEMERA follows an open science policy. This means that deliverables and related datasets will be freely available, if they are labelled as "Public" through the definition of the governing data licenses and as provided in the project deliverables' table.

In all other cases, a publishable version of the document will be produced and shared via the same mechanisms. Also, all scientific and research papers will be openly available for free. Those papers may be article pre-prints, peer-reviewed articles in scholar journals, articles in conference proceedings, monographs, patents, etc.

2.6.2. Early-stage sharing

All publicly available dissemination materials will be published at the earliest possible time. Relevant partners will be completing pre-registrations at publishers. Whereas pre-print versions of articles will first be deposited on open-access repositories.

2.6.3. Reaching high visibility

Final versions of articles and other public scientific output will be deposited to institutional open-access repositories that feed into OpenAIRE together with the articles that potentially increase and maximize impact among the scientific community, policy makers and the business sector. These materials will also be uploaded to Horizon Results Platform to gain wider uptake and visibility.

2.6.4. Reproducibility

Access will be assured to all sort of research background data to ensure validation and reproducibility of research and project outputs. A more detailed, individual data management plan is going to be produced in the project to clarify and introduce the strategy and details of data management throughout the project.

2.7. Rights and obligations related to knowledge and results

Based on the terms of the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement the knowledge and results generated within the project should be openly available. Doing so should facilitate the adoption of any project output.

2.7.1. IPR Agreements

Intellectual property right (IPR) of a result is owned by the contributing partner who has contributed to that project result. A third party (licensee) is allowed to request a license

3.2. Schedule of activities

The timing and schedule of communication and dissemination activities in the project are based on the grant agreement and further discussions with the Partners.

It was agreed to be efficient setting up an initial schedule for the term M1-6, and for the rest of the project term (M7-36). Proceeding further with the project though, the Partners can decide on making further divisions and schedule if needed.

3.2.1. Scheduled activities for M1-6

- Developing the project website
- Developing the project visual identity
- Mapping stakeholders – mapping and identifying stakeholders of multiple groups for engagement
- Initiating and developing social media channels
- Supporting Partners with initiating AGEMERA communication activities in their organization and within their environment/community
- Initiating networking and dissemination activities – social media presence, press release, attendance at conference
- First project video completed and available
- Creating dissemination materials – general posters, roll-ups and leaflets printed in English

3.2.2. Scheduled activities for M7-36

- Further networking and dissemination activities
- Continuous presence via newsletters and post on the news feed
- Further project videos
- Further events
- Further scientific articles

3.3. Internal communication coordination to promote better external communication

The management of tasks in WP5 will require close cooperation with both the Project Coordinator and the Partners.

The leader of WP5 is going to attend on the regular WP leaders' meeting organized by the coordinator, in order to inform the WP Leaders about proceedings and developments occurred, relevant tasks and potential issues. The WP5 leader also organizes regular meetings with all the partners related to the WP, for the purpose of navigating the tasks, delegating subtasks, and tracking activities related to communication and dissemination.

3.4. Budget and resources

Personnel effort as well as purchase costs have been planned for all partners to actively contribute to dissemination and communication activities. These data (person-month allocation per partner in WP5 and purchase costs in WP5) are available in the relevant part of the AGEMERA GA.

3.5. Targets and KPIs

Track	M6	M6-24	M24-36	KPI (cumulative)
Social media campaigns	Twitter Facebook LinkedIn	Twitter Facebook LinkedIn	Twitter Facebook LinkedIn	Twitter followers = 1,000 LinkedIn group members = 2,000
Project video	1 Video	1 Video	1 Video	Total YouTube views = 20,000
Press releases	Press release 1	Press release 2 Press release 3	Press release 4 Press release 5	Total PR coverage (incl. online articles) = 500
Posters	1 submission	3 submissions	4 submissions	Total posters = 8
Publications	1 submission	3 submissions	6 submissions	Total publications = 10
Articles	3 articles	12 articles	20 articles	Total articles = 35
Workshops	-	-	4 workshops	Total attendees = 480
CRM educational package	-	1,000 visitors	10,000 visitors (cumulative)	Total reach= 10,000 visitors
CRM serious game	-	-	500	Total reach= 500 game sessions

3.6. Distribution of Tasks

GEO is responsible for the overall coordination of dissemination and communication activities.

The internal general workflow is the following:

Partners are informed about their role in WP5 and the work they need to pay attention to, to deliver project tasks efficiently and meet the objectives marked by the project.

All other partners will have the following general responsibilities and tasks:

Acknowledgement and internal exchange of ideas:

- Reading the dissemination guidelines and following them
- Contributing with requested data to Dissemination and Communication Plan
- Contributing and participating in approving the COMM action plans, social media messages and content calendar (e.g. blogs and articles)
- Showing proactivity, and sending GEO best practices that should be applied such as infographics and other visual ideas
- Using AGEMERA's dissemination templates and materials
- Letting WP5 Leaders know in advance when attending an event, or being covered in local media, etc.

Reporting:

- Reporting sheets must be filled in before the 3-monthly meetings
- Informing the core COMM team and GEO about events, news, national campaigns to be able to support you
- Documenting and archiving all AGEMERA related communication and dissemination activities (photos, list of attendees, sample material, etc.), besides the regular tracking.

Actions to increase visibility:

- Informing your network members
- Providing translations on relevant AGEMERA news and share those locally
- Engaging press and media contacts
- Update your organizations' websites with information on AGEMERA and your involvement (e.g. a news item).
- Linking your social media accounts to AGEMERA accounts (follow, regularly re-tweet, share).
- Contributing to the posts (blogs, news, social media, etc.) by sharing, commenting, etc.
- Sending WP5 Leaders the relevant news and event information.

4. Reporting and monitoring

4.1. Reporting and monitoring at partners' level

WP5 Leader will instruct and monitor each partner organisation on reporting and monitoring tasks. Reporting will be aligned with Horizon Europe requests and EC demands. KPIs will be strictly monitored throughout the project duration. Regular meetings will be set up amongst the people who will be in charge of communicating and disseminating about AGEMERA's project at company level.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G
1	AGEMERA						
2							
3							
4							
5							
6	1. Dissemination activities	All partners shall fill in the sheet with the activities THEY performed at least on a 6-monthly basis.					
7	2. Communication activities	All partners shall fill in the sheet with the activities THEY performed at least on a 3-monthly basis.					
8	3. Press & Media	All partners shall report any coverage of THE PROJECT EXTERNALLY at a local level (e.g. interviews, reposting partner news, cross-references, promotion, etc.)					
9	4. Scientific Publications	To be filled in at the time of publication - at the latest towards the second half of the project.					
10	5. KPIs	Targets are listed for the reference of each partner. Geonardo will be filling these in on a three monthly basis.					
11	Proposed activities	Use the Teams thread or send an e-mail to share your ideas for events, dissemination material, campaigns etc.					
12							
13							
14							
15							
16							
17							
18							
19							
20							
21							
22							

Image 8 Internal reporting and monitoring table for dissemination and communication activities

4.2. Reporting and monitoring at Project level

As well as reporting and monitoring the partners' communication efforts, GEO will carefully analyse and report on social media and website analytics to ensure communication efforts are well distributed and are achieving the expected communication objectives.

Some of the platforms that will be used to monitor AGEMERA's communication results are Social Media Insights and Google Analytics.

ANNEX: AGEMERA VISUAL IDENTITY – Brand Manual & Guidelines

